

Heritage in Emergency: Ukraine

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Keywords

Ukraine, cultural heritage, Russia-Ukraine war,
higher education, solidarity

Date

April 14, 2025

Abstract

The article examines the democratic world's responses to the emergencies that have affected Ukraine's cultural heritage, both tangible and intangible, since 2022, when Russia launched a full-scale military invasion of Ukraine. The focus is on the initiatives the authors have tracked by the higher education institutions in different European countries and beyond. Seven case studies are analysed in more detail.

Introduction

Russia's invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022, prompted immediate condemnation from global democracies, calling for action both at the governmental level and within society as a whole. The conflicts in the Middle East since the turn of the 21st century, which have fuelled brutal campaigns of CH destruction by the Taliban, Al Qaeda, and the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS), have much in common with Russia's current military manifestations in Ukraine. There is an invitation to see the conflict-related destruction of cultural heritage (CH) not solely as

a “cultural tragedy” but as a “security issue” (Rosén 2022: 5), emphasises the active role of CH in the war situation.

In the context of war and its emergencies, the usual peacetime scenarios of CH conservation and planning are frequently replaced by rapid, unexpected solutions and new cooperations. At the outbreak of the Russia-Ukraine war, such a global player as UNESCO took corresponding action by aiming to identify and protect cultural places in Ukraine from bombardments, by promoting satellite monitoring of the damage, and by enquiring about needs Ukrainian cultural professionals, among them World Heritage site managers, museum directors and professionals in charge of immovable and movable heritage. Audrey Azoulay, UNESCO Director-General, argued for action to save CH in Ukraine in the following way: “We must safeguard the cultural heritage in Ukraine, as a testimony of the past but also as a catalyst for peace and cohesion for the future, which the international community has to protect and preserve.” (Endangered heritage in Ukraine, 2022). However, many efforts, on a smaller scale, have been carried out with similar zeal. There is a wide variety of social actors and numerous individuals involved in different capacities in actions to protect, document, restore, research, and raise the awareness and visibility of Ukraine’s CH.

This article seeks to identify and understand the efforts in favour of Ukrainian CH, as demonstrated by the higher education institutions (HEI) in Ukraine and beyond over the past three years. How has democratic society mobilised around Ukraine’s CH in the context of the Russia-Ukraine war? What kind of initiatives have been launched and carried out by the HEI? What bilateral and international collaborations have been developed? How have priorities for tangible and intangible cultural heritage (ICH) been positioned? How important are digital capabilities and components for the actions taken? An analysis of publicly available information sources will be conducted to answer these research questions. Immediate HEI initiatives deserve both a summative analysis and a closer look, which will be done through a set of seven case studies.

HEI Responses to CH Emergencies

One of the primary activities in understanding the role of HEI actors supporting Ukraine's endangered CH was data collection. In this phase, we focused on two types of information, which we respectively organized into two inventories:

A1 – “International HEI responses to CH emergency in wartime Ukraine” and

A2 – “University actors as agents of change in digital CH for crisis responsiveness”.

A total of 103 initiatives from 24 countries were studied (Fig. 1). All around the globe there were efforts made by an academic community to mitigate the cultural emergency in Ukraine, however, European nations played a key role.

Fig. 1. Geographical distribution of the studied initiatives

HEI demonstrate a significant international commitment to sustaining Ukraine (see Fig. 2). The collaboration highlights how important HEI are in the field of heritage preservation as they provide knowledge, manpower and platforms for international cooperation. There are only 14% of studied initiatives from within Ukraine alone showing constraints faced by the local institutions and organisations while they pursue conservation during the ongoing war. Such a large proportion (69%) of international projects reflects global solidarity and worldwide recognition of the signi-

ificance of Ukraine’s cultural legacy, which has motivated various actors across continents to make contributions towards its safeguarding.

Fig. 2. Share of the HEI initiatives

The A1 inventory list captures a broad spectrum of actions driven by HEI in support of Ukrainian CH since February of 2022. It serves to document the various ways in which many academic institutions have contributed to preservation of CH, providing a comprehensive overview of efforts that can be used for further research, policy-making, and implementation of best practices. The A2 inventory list highlights grassroots and personally initiated efforts by individuals associated with HEI, including academics, researchers, administrative staff, and students, in support of Ukraine’s CH.

The data collection was conducted, employing a combination of desktop research and systematic documentation. A structured approach was used to identify and compile information on the HEI-related initiatives supporting Ukrainian heritage. This process involved exploring the web using specific keywords in different languages to ensure comprehensive coverage. Primary data sources included direct contributions from HEI representatives, official reports, institutional websites, and other pertinent publications. The entries were systematically categorized based on key attributes such as the type of social action, the status of the project

(ongoing or past), and its connection to the recent CH emergency in Ukraine. Each entry was structured to provide a clear and concise overview, with additional details accessible through embedded links.

Both inventories highlight the diverse strategies employed by HEI and their staff to support Ukrainian CH during the war. The A1 inventory emphasises initiatives led by universities involving direct support, such as providing logistical assistance and essential equipment to Ukrainian cultural institutions to protect and maintain cultural artefacts and records. Additionally, A1 captures educational and community outreach efforts, where universities offer training and capacity-building programs to enhance local expertise in CH preservation. Similarly, the A2 inventory highlights projects related to digital archiving and documentation of war damage. It includes initiatives focusing on social media campaigns, virtual exhibitions, fundraising activities, and the use of digital platforms to raise awareness and engage the global community. Together, these inventories illustrate the comprehensive efforts by HEI and the academic community to safeguard and promote Ukrainian CH amidst the challenges of war.

Close-up on Initiatives

From the entire number of initiatives, a closer look at seven follows. This selected set of cases is designed to present the diversity of efforts, with focus both on the tangible and intangible CH.

(1) The Center to Rescue Cultural Heritage (CRCH) in Lviv, Ukraine, is a good example of quick mobilisation and international partnership. It was established on March 1st, 2022, with a mandate to save Ukrainian CH which is under direct threat. Recognizing that cultural artefacts must be protected from destruction, the CRCH was organised by people working within the culture sector and academics. The key tasks were identification of endangered objects, provision of necessary conservation resources, and communication with international partners regarding financial and material assistance (Lviv Polytechnic National University, 2023). The Center provides extensive documentation and monitoring of CH sites thereby making detailed records useful for immediate protection as well as the post-war re-

covery purposes. Direct conservation activities involve packaging up items with specialised materials, fire protection systems, etc. Lviv Polytechnic National University functions as a base of logistics and operations and integrates academic expertise into the conservation efforts through research, fieldwork, and volunteers (ICON, 2023).

To ensure that the Centre's approaches are based on current research and best practices in heritage preservation, support is sought from other HEI and research institutions in Europe, such as the University Museum of Bergen (Norway). HEI also have an important role to play in educational projects of the Centre to provide capacity-building workshops, seminars, and training for local communities toward heritage conservation. Furthermore, the CRCH entails an integrated approach that combines immediate protection measures with long-term strategies for restoration and education. War-damaged cultural sites are properly documented, thus ensuring that there are immediate conservation efforts being put in place for them when attacked by war and later used as a guide during future restoration projects (UNESCO, 2023: 104–112).

This initiative shows how cultural professionals working together with educational institutions can establish a strong model of preserving heritage during war emergencies. Besides, it underlies the importance of CH as a manifestation of national identity and emphasises that history and culture need special care in the wartime.

(2) The Second Scientific and Practical Conference, “Food in History”, sought to investigate food's role in shaping cultural practices in times of war. It was initially scheduled for 2022, but due to the military conflict, it was postponed to January 2023. Organized by the Centre for Food Studies together with MIKS (urban studies journal) and the History Department of Kyiv National University, the online conference showed how resilient Ukrainian scholars have been while carrying out their research despite the war (Yizhakultura, 2023).

The main intention of the conference was to record changing food trends related to the war time. Seeing food as a medium of culture, this academic event aimed to

provide valuable data for further studies and policymaking that could help preserve Ukraine's CH. Through food-oriented routines and stories, the multidisciplinary conference tried to register social transformations occasioned by war and document Ukrainians' lived experiences. With methodological diversity, the researchers revealed how food practices intersected with cultural identity and social resilience.

The scholars stressed the cultural importance of food during the war. One theme was memes about food. It was shown how jokes and pictures of food served as mechanisms of defense and coping for people at war. The second theme was personal accounts during the occupation and the role of food in everyday life. The findings showed how cooking food and searching for it acted like a stress reliever, which helped people bond with one another despite facing hard times. As a result, the "War Cookbook" Project allowed the stakeholders to document Ukrainian gastronomy during the war years, thus allowing us to understand better the connections between wartime experience and the foods people eat. CH preservation is one reason this project observed such practices, while others have explored different ways individuals adapt their eating habits when fighting wars (Zagoriy Foundation, 2023).

Survival strategies in occupied territories also showed how important communal support systems were alongside ritualised approaches to meals. In northeastern Ukraine, ethnographic research was conducted on individuals' survival strategies and the economic aspects of food production in small towns. The findings showed that traditional farming methods were still resilient enough to guarantee efficient self-reliance.

The conference demonstrated how important it was for HEI to preserve and give visibility to CH through collaborative research. By involving researchers, students, and other members of the HE academic community in this knowledge dissemination activity, HE specialists and the general public were reached with the aim of enhancing cultural resilience in Ukraine.

(3) UMAC for Ukrainian museums. Immediately after the Russian aggression in 2022, the International Council of Museums (ICOM) denounced any damage posed to CH in Ukraine and urged relevant stakeholders to support museums and their staff. At the operational level, ICOM collaborated closely with Ukrainian and international stakeholders to meet the challenges and to support Ukrainian museums with the necessary resources. They were convened during the General Conference of ICOM in August 2022 in Prague. During the event, Dr. Svitlana Muravska from Lviv Polytechnic National University reported on the situation in Lviv during the war, which took place at the panel of the Committee of ICOM for University Museums and Collections (UMAC) at Charles University in Prague, Czechia. (Verbytska, Muravska, 2023)

An essential consequence of ICOM Prague 2022 was an online meeting of the Ukrainian University and the Ukrainian community on 29 September 2022, initiated by UMAC and Svitlana Muravska, a member of ICOM UMAC Ukraine. This dedicated event aimed to highlight ongoing initiatives and foster dialogue. It was a crucial step in the ongoing process of supporting university museums in Ukraine in times of war.

During the meeting, Ukrainian museum staff had the opportunity to share their professional experience of university museums and efforts at rescuing their collections during the new stage of the war in Ukraine caused by Russian aggression. The circumstances of the following university museums were highlighted: Museum of Nature of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University; Museum of Archaeology of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University; Museum Complex of H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University; Nizhyn Museum complex of the Nizhyn Gogol State University; Archaeological Museum of Kherson State University; Archaeological Museum of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv.

In the second part of the meeting, representatives of Ukrainian and international cultural organizations participated in the discussion on the urgent problems of Ukrainian university museums. The experts exchanged views on the changes university museums in Ukraine underwent during the war. According to the debate

participants, the most pressing problems were the loss of professionals and collections, evacuation of museums, low salaries of museum workers, and the state's overall economic losses in the war, which led to a reduction in cultural funding. Representatives of the international museum network expressed unconditional support for Ukrainian university museums. They encouraged the Ukrainian museums to articulate their needs, as this would facilitate the provision of necessary assistance. (UMAC, 2022)

After the meeting, thanks to the significant humanitarian aid received by the museums from various organizations in Ukraine, Poland, Germany, Switzerland, and other countries, work with the collections continued, and it became possible to begin conserving objects. Dozens of museums in different regions of Ukraine, including university museums, received the necessary assistance with the support of the international non-governmental organization World Heritage Watch, the German Ministry of Culture, and the Ukraine Art Aid Centre from Germany. (Kazantseva, Samoilenko, Pysarevska, 2023)

The meeting with Ukrainian university museum workers was a vivid example of international solidarity, and such was the assistance that followed this meeting. The joint sharing and discussion concluded that, in times of war, the university museums have to use all possible means to minimize the effects of the damage already done and to use modern packaging methods, digitization, and preservation of their holdings. The professional upgrading of museum staff was seen as urgent. Many ICOM member countries are now taking responsibility for supporting university museums in Ukraine. This initiative was primarily made possible through international professional networking, including the meeting of 29 September 2022.

(4) Research project “Digital Documentation of Inscriptions in the Sofia Cathedral in Kyiv” (“Digital dokumentation av inskriptioner i Sofiakatedralen i Kiev”) was carried out by Gothenburg Research Infrastructure in Digital Humanities (GRIDH) at the University of Gothenburg and Museum of St. Sophia Cathedral in Kyiv. The project run from 2023 to the end of 2024. It was implemented by Professor Gunnar Almevik and Research Coordinator, Jonathan

Westin from the University of Gothenburg, as well as a group of professionals and scientists from Ukraine.

The aim of the project was to use digital methods to document the inscriptions found in St. Sophia's Cathedral. The project provided scholars with access to endangered CH source material and made it available to the public. The aim was to provide highly readable 3D models and other digital representations of the inscriptions as a basis for future research. The data are available through a portal with an easy-to-navigate public interface specifically designed for inscription review, provided by the GRIDH (University of Gothenburg, 2024a) at the address <https://saintsophia.dh.gu.se/>.

According to the project's website (University of Gothenburg, 2024b), St. Sophia's Cathedral inscriptions have been documented since the 1960s, with around 7000 inscriptions recorded to date. However, earlier documentation is not widely available. There is confusion as to how the various cut marks are to be interpreted as signs and how the signs are to be interpreted as language and meaning. The digital documentation technologies available today make it possible to present high-definition primary source material for research in different languages and disciplines, and the opportunities presented by digital humanities and other disciplines enable researchers to interpret these historical records and exchange ideas. As professor of Digital Cultural Heritage Maria Economou wrote: "The use of digital tools can help specialists and professionals organize the large amount of data involved in the scientific investigation and recording of the past, but they can also make these more understandable to a wide audience." (Economou, 2015: 217) This was also the intention of the authors of the initiative in question, which only proves its high value. In January 2024, Swedish researchers travelled to Kyiv to begin the first work on documenting the wall inscriptions, using a variety of methods, e.g., 3D scanning and laser capabilities. They also trained a team from Ukraine so that they can carry out substantial work themselves in the following years.

St. Sophia Cathedral, which has the largest preserved collection of mosaics and frescoes from that era, is a singular example of early 11th-century monumental art and architecture. The Cathedral's massive adornment is a remarkable example of

Byzantine art and a unique ensemble whose conceptual design represents the main religious concepts of the day. The Cathedral's mural paintings also feature a series of distinctive secular frescoes in the stair towers that are created in the Byzantine art tradition. (UNESCO, 1990) The "European Gold Medal for the Protection of Historic Monuments" was given to St. Sophia's restoration efforts in 1987. The St. Sophia Cathedral and associated monastic structures serve as a museum for both official functions and educational reasons.

In 1990, the St. Sophia Cathedral and related monastic buildings, Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List (UNESCO, 1990). The UNESCO report from 2023 stated: "Currently, the property faces not only the risk of a direct hit by Russian missiles and drones but also the impact of shock and sound waves from the bombing of the city. Vibration loads may cause deterioration of the load-bearing capacity of the property's structures and provoke a significant threat in the detachment of mosaics and ancient plaster decorated with frescoes. An additional threat is associated with emergency and rolling blackouts resulting in the shutdown of special equipment that maintains constant conditions at the property (microclimate, etc.)." (UNESCO, 2023: 112) For these reasons, the Cathedral and the surrounding complex have also been inscribed on UNESCO's List of World Heritage in Danger.

What is important about this project is that it documented the signs and drawings found on the walls, thus preserving the material CH. The implemented project not only has made the Ukrainian heritage accessible to anybody in the world, but also provided valuable data for research. This is also important in terms of preserving ICH – ancient languages (e.g. Slavonic, Latin, Armenian, Greek), their signs, written material provides information about ancient cultures and linguistic expressions, societal communication and values. The more data there is, the more interpretation possibilities there are. In this project, it was important to focus on one object and to document, preserve, and study it from different angles in order to get as in-depth a view as possible. This is a good example of the need for the skills and experience of researchers in HE, especially in this case where the Swedish researchers are highly experienced in the digital preservation, interpretation and communication of endangered heritage. Passing on their knowl-

edge to Ukrainian experts and scientists so they can continue their work in Ukraine. Their knowledge will most likely will also be passed on to the students who will work alongside the scientists. It should also be noted that the accumulated data can be stored on different servers, thus providing more copies in different parts of the world in case one of the servers is destroyed.

This example is a good illustration of HE representatives helping one institution in Ukraine, with more far-reaching consequences, creating widely available data, as well as knowledge that will be useful not only for students and researchers in the future, but for society in general.

(5) Research “Profiles of Resistance and Resilience: Documenting looting, damage, and destruction of Ukrainian Cultural Heritage”. New initiatives sometimes build on older collaborations – Ukrainian Catholic University (UCU, Ukraine) and the University of Notre Dame (ND, USA) have worked together for almost 20 years, going on exchange trips to gain experience elsewhere. In 2022, when the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine began, the university partners quickly created new opportunities for students, faculty, and administrators. ND hosted students on campus for a semester, providing accommodation, living expenses, and other necessary costs. This part of the initiative has been running for several semesters, allowing students to learn new skills in a more relaxed environment, which they can then apply in Ukraine.

Administrators have also been invited to participate in leadership and capacity-building workshops. ND established faculty fellowships, which enabled the creation of a course or curriculum with faculty members. They also offered faculty grant programs, research collaboration, curriculum, course development, and library research grants, encouraging partners from both institutions to work together on a joint project. (Pippenger, 2023) This wide range of initiatives has not gone unnoticed, not only appreciated by all stakeholders but also – this initiative was awarded the 2023 Institute of International Education Heiskell Award for Strategic Partnerships. (Pippenger, 2023)

Professors Ian Kuijt and Bill Donaruma, interested in archaeology, anthropology, and filmmaking, were part of the initiative – they created this research. They worked with Ukrainian students, training them in archaeology and the basics of documentary filmmaking so that they could then identify, record, and preserve their culture, which is currently in a precarious state because it could be affected by war at any moment. As one of the professors said: “The Russian invasion is not just a military invasion, it is an attempt to destroy Ukrainian heritage and culture.” (University of Notre Dame, 2023) Understandably, culture, language, customs and habits, rituals, and celebration of festivals are also targeted in war to destroy what is specific to the nation. After working in Ukraine, the project participants made a short video highlighting the challenges in Ukraine, particularly the preservation of CH. (@NotreDame, 2023) Moreover, they also wrote an essay on how CH is affected by war. This is not only done by deliberately destroying and stealing it, but also by digging trenches into archaeological heritage, which was previously unexplored. It is understandable that this is and will be done in war. As the authors wrote: “Ukraine’s churches, museums, and libraries are a threat to Russia, for they are the material and symbolic fabric that holds together Ukrainian identity and resistance. That is why this war is as much about culture as it is about land.” (Kuijt, Shydlovskyi, Donaruma, 2024) That is why such a more ethereal project is also very valuable. The ND professors in Lviv particularly worked with the students on storytelling skills. The way stories are told to the wider public, both about the tangible CH destroyed by war and the immaterial values, fates, and experiences of people, has far-reaching consequences. One of these stories was also presented at ND – a special museum exhibit at the History Museum in South Bend, Indiana, was created, sharing the stories of Ukrainian students and lecturers about what is happening in Ukraine, including information on Ukraine’s CH, which is being destroyed by the war.

Technology plays an important role in this collaboration between the two universities, not only the usual ones for communication but also the professors mentioned above worked with various environmental and object scanning equipment (e.g., photogrammetry on quad-copters) while in Lviv to record monuments, buildings, and space. There have also been joint study courses online for American and Ukrainian students. (Lingle, Skendzel, Votava, 2024) This

collaboration between students from both countries allowed for an exchange of different points of view and also allowed the Ukrainian students to clearly and explicitly tell their colleagues what was happening in their country and how their understanding of cultural values had changed.

One of the results of the initiative is the collection of essays “Resilient Universities” (Turchynovskyy, 2024). Several experts share theoretical insights, experiences, and case studies related to the topic. Importantly, it seems to stress the need for HEI to maintain continuity. At each stage of the threat, however, different operating principles apply: “During the survival period of an adversity, be especially sensitive to the wellbeing of individuals; during the rebuild period, be especially sensitive to new collaborations and unused skills; during the consolidation period, revisit the lessons learned from the crisis mode.” (Turchynovskyy, 2024: 32) It also stresses that it will not be possible to return to the same place where the change occurred after the disturbance. Although not directly related to CH, this collection provides valuable insights into the functioning and principles of HEI in times of war and various turbulences. However, it is also possible to relate to intangible culture in a broader sense, including various values, beliefs, and ethical considerations that are important in the work of HEI.

This cooperation between Ukraine and the US universities is important because it is long-lasting, so existing contacts help to establish new initiatives more quickly, identify needs, and understand the environment in which colleagues work. HEI significantly contributes to the preservation, identification, and subsequent development of ideas for the restoration of CH, both tangible and intangible. Practical assistance (remotely and on the ground) and communication with the broader public on the impact of war on preservation, as well as cooperation on educational issues – exchange programmes, and joint courses of study. There is no doubt that these HEI will continue to work together. This initiative is a good example of a valuable long-term cooperation based on shared values.

(6) Archaeological Landscapes Monitoring Group. The Russian invasion of Ukraine has destroyed or damaged thousands of Ukrainian CH sites, many of which are subterranean and previously undocumented. Monitoring CH destruction is carried out at the state level and through civic initiatives. However, the analysis of losses is limited mainly to cultural objects, monumental art, architecture, and religious buildings. (Buiskykh, Shydlovskiy, Ivakin, 2023) Thus, recording the destruction of archaeological heritage (AH) sites due to certain peculiarities is crucial, and significant difficulties are encountered. Paradoxically, the destruction of landscapes due to warfare often leads to the discovery of archaeological sites. Practical lack of control over the condition of archaeological sites by state executive authorities also leads to activities of marauding and looting groups about AH objects. (NASU Institute of Archaeology, 2022)

In order to solve problems in the field of documenting damage to AH, representatives of several scientific, educational, and museum institutions have created an interdisciplinary Archaeological Landscape Monitoring Group, whose task is to record losses at archaeological sites. The work of the group was carried out in the territories of Kyiv, Chernihiv, and Mykolaiv regions within the framework of the project of the German Archaeological Institute under the pilot program “Ukrainian Archaeological Heritage Threatened by War: Saving and Protection.” (German Archaeological Institute, 2022)

The working group consisted of archaeologists and monument conservationists from different Ukrainian institutions and organizations: Institute of Archeology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine; Ukrainian State Institute of Cultural Heritage; History Department of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; National Museum of History of Ukraine; National Reserve “Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra”; NGO “Union of Archaeologists of Ukraine” and many other concerned volunteers. (Shydlovskiy, Kuijt, Skorokhod et al., 2023) The research was conducted in partnership with scholars from the University of Notre Dame, USA, and was funded by the German Archaeological Institute.

The main result of monitoring of archaeological sites in Kyiv and Chernihiv regions within this initiative is the development of a methodology and the acquisition of

experience in extremely difficult conditions of research work. An accurate determination of the damage is possible with remote monitoring methods of AH sites and visual inspection by archaeologists of specific locations of damage to areas of the historical and cultural layer. Given the ongoing hostilities, scientists, specialists in CH preservation organisations, and public activists have to gather information about the extent and nature of damage to archaeological sites.

It is worth noting that the international project team allowed the introduction of an innovative methodology of multi-stage process identification and documentation of damaged CH in Ukraine. International partners contributed to new approaches to monitoring destruction and damage to archaeological sites and their recording, as well as the creation of an electronic database of such facts. Based on the reports received from the monitoring activities, an electronic database was created at the Institute of Archaeology. The reports and acts form the basis for future claims of Ukraine against the aggressor state for compensation and damage to the AH. (Chernyshuk, 2023)

In 2022, the German Archaeological Institute initiated scholarships for Ukrainian archaeologists. In 2023, project activities were supported in the challenging tasks of documenting, preserving, and rescuing AH amid the conflict under financing by the German Federal Foreign Office. The projects selected encompass diverse activities, including 3D recording and documentation of destroyed archaeological sites, excavation efforts in conflict zones, cataloguing and digital preservation of research findings and museum collections, archaeological analysis, and the publication of results. (German Archaeological Institute, 2023) Representatives of universities, including faculty members from the University of Notre Dame, USA, and the Department of Archeology at Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, actively participated in the archaeological monitoring. The participation of university professors in the project not only ensured the proper academic and level of the research, analysis, and publication of scientific results and provided its educational component. New methods of research, documentation, and recording of AH losses are being introduced into the educational process of training students thanks to an active member of the project team, Associate Professor Pavlo Shydlovskiy, PhD in History. On May 16, 2024, a panel discussion, "Archaeologi-

cal Heritage in the Context of Military Conflicts in Ukraine,” was held at the Faculty of History of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, where Pavlo Shydlovsky and his colleague from the Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies Yevhen Synitsia were the speakers. (Scientific Society of Students of the Faculty of History of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, 2024)

Field research is an essential component of archaeology. In July-August 2024, students of the 3rd-4th year of the educational program “Archaeology and Prehistory” of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv took part in the Polish-Ukrainian Summer Archaeological School “Common Heritage” (Polsko-ukraińska szkoła letnia “Wspólne Dziedzictwo”). The organizers and implementers of the international project are the Society of Friends of the Institute of Archaeology of the Polish Academy of Sciences and the Department of Early Slavic Archaeology of the Institute of Archaeology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine under financial and support of the Polish-American RITA Foundation. (Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies, 2024)

The project includes three stages (Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies, 2024). The first stage, theoretical, aims to familiarize students with the current state of protection of AH in Ukraine and Poland, the results and prospects of research on the archaeology of Bukovyna, in particular on the example of the monuments of Komariv and Buzovytsia. The second stage was hands-on, practical field archaeological research during the Komariv expedition. In the third stage, the students presented their pilot projects and shared their impressions and feedback about the event. The school was not only attended by students from Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv but also by students from Ternopil V. Hnatiuk National Pedagogical University, Ukrainian State Dragomanov University, and Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, making it a truly collaborative and enriching experience.

Thus, the archaeological monitoring conducted by the Archaeological Landscapes Monitoring Group in Ukraine has highlighted the scale of damage to subterranean CH. This underscores the crucial role that each stakeholder, including government officials, archaeologists, CH preservation organizations, and universities on both

Ukrainian and international levels, plays in preserving the CH. Understanding the nature of the destruction of AH has demonstrated the need to upgrade the archaeological sites' registration system and establish databases for monuments integrated with the digital mapping of territories impacted by military activities. The initiative's results have demonstrated the necessity for initial and professional training of specialists in archaeology, further empowering the role of the HEI.

(7) “Building bridges: cultural exchange for all”. At the end of the first year of the war, in November and December of 2022, the Centre of Ukraine at Vytautas Magnus University in Lithuania implemented a project, “Building bridges: cultural exchange for all”. The project aimed at introducing Ukrainian CH, history and various art forms to wider audiences in Lithuania thus raising visibility and awareness of Ukrainian culture for locals in the war refugees' host country. The bridge metaphor in the project's title thus pointed towards building connections through culture, introducing and enriching the community of newly-arrived Ukrainian war refugees as well as long-term residents of Ukrainian origin, who are professionals in various fields, also activists, and the local Vilnius society, both Lithuanians and ethnic minorities, including Russians and Poles. A further objective has been to establish a basis for further cooperation in the cultural sector between Ukrainians currently residing in Lithuania and relevant cultural sector players in Lithuania.

Although the project duration was relatively short, it included a wide range of face-to-face activities, thematic culture events and Ukrainian holiday events focusing mainly on the ICH of Ukraine, namely, Ukrainian people's knowledge, skills, traditions and living expressions, brought with them to Lithuania when they fled their homeland. The planned 4-6 events involved performances of traditional Ukrainian singing, folk dancing, playing the bandura, the national Ukrainian musical instrument, participation of the traditional vyshivanka embroiderers and others. The traditions of celebrations and commemorations were naturally aligned by the project implementers with the Ukrainian calendar of holidays and commemorations during the months of project implementation. Thus, the special days, which on the one hand allowed for the celebration of the refugee community, and on the other were a manifestation of Ukrainian culture addressed to the Lithu-

anian population, were Ukrainian winter holidays and Holodomor Memorial Day. Alongside these cultural events, the project also held a series of integration workshops and English and Lithuanian language clubs. The audience was all generations, including children, youth and adults.

The initiative was funded by the European Cultural Foundation. As Russia's war in Ukraine intensified, the Fund enabled the European cultural sector to programme Ukrainian arts and culture. Being one of 15 of the Culture of Solidarity Fund EUNIC (the network of EU National Institutes for Culture) Ukraine edition grantees in 2022, the Centre of Ukraine at Vytautas Magnus University followed the mission of the financing programme to foster the need to get to know Ukraine, a new European Union candidate country, in the grantee countries. (Culture of Solidarity .., 2022) After completion of the project, its implementers acknowledged the success of the plans and pointed out that "Building bridges: cultural exchange for all" left a significant meaning both for the Ukrainian and Lithuanian communities. (Building Bridges, 2023) It is evident that the project has been a good example of balancing long-term strategic goals, including the integration of the Ukrainian community in Lithuania, and the needs of different generations of the community to socialise, have a sense of belonging and educational opportunities through the enhancement of Ukrainian ICH.

The project was one of the first for the Centre of Ukraine in the initial year of its establishment. As a structural unit of the Vytautas Magnus University, the Centre of Ukraine nevertheless operates quite autonomously and is not directly linked to academic processes. It is located at the premises of Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy in Vilnius, whereas the main seat of the University and its historical structural units are based in Kaunas, former capital and the second largest city of Lithuania. The Centre of Ukraine was opened on 11 June 2022 through cooperative efforts of the Presidency of the Republic of Lithuania, the Embassy of Ukraine in Lithuania and Vytautas Magnus University. Among the main tasks declared by the Centre were mobilisation of intellectual potential, presenting Ukraine and its culture in Lithuania on a broader international scale, supporting Ukraine in preparation for membership in the European Union as well as providing psychological, legal and pedagogical assistance to the war refugees.

At the time of its launch, the Centre's initiators were proud to call it the first centre of its kind in the world (Centre of Ukraine .., 2022). The CH is highlighted in the Centre's short-term strategic objectives as commitment to "develop and promote Ukraine's CH in Lithuania, including art, music, poetry, sculpture, history, geography, culinary, and folklore heritage" (Latysh, Didenko, 2023: 9).

The creation of the Centre of Ukraine and its activities undoubtedly fall within the sphere of cultural diplomacy, wherein, as researchers have noted, CH plays the role of a "social barometer" from which to determine the cultural policies to be implemented (Lee, Niglio, 2019: 227-223). Ukrainian CH is still constantly on the agenda of the Centre's projects and activities.

These case studies show that there are many creative emergency-driven ways in which actors from HEI can be involved in the safeguarding, preservation and raising the visibility of Ukraine's tangible and intangible CH. Our research aims at increasing knowledge and understanding of actions taken so far, and it can also serve as an encouragement for further stakeholder engagement in different capacities, locally, regionally or in a broad international scope.

Conclusions

When in the midst of an ongoing civil war, endless attempts were made to preserve Ukrainian CH. It is a testament to their indomitable spirit, adaptability and global cooperation. This ensures that these tangible and intangible elements are maintained and preserved using various methods such as documentation and digitization as well as emergency response and public involvement in CH protection endeavours.

Such moves would not be possible without HEI which provide both intellectual and logistical backup for them. This helps to bring research closer to the field during heritage safeguarding activities. Such institutions promote cross-disciplinary dialogue thus increasing a range of perspectives on preservation actions for the future. They also act as transfer points for aid supplies, relief materials, logistic bases distributing humanitarian assistance and host facilities dedicated to preserving Ukrainian CH.

International collaboration makes these initiatives more impactful. While there are many challenges in the field of CH in a war context, cooperation between local and international partners allows for more rapid research and identifies areas where additional resources and expertise are needed. And by identifying such sectors, by addressing them in depth, both at the grassroots level and at the level of researchers and experts, heritage can also be better preserved for future generations.

International groups and consortia working beyond the national level are a strong manifestation of solidarity with the war-torn Ukraine in the democratic world, whose concern for Ukraine's CH will serve both the specific tasks at hand and also, hopefully, the strengthening of peace in the future. These actions taken are not only a response to the circumstances dictated by the Russian war but also an appreciation of Ukraine's CH on a global level.

References

- @NotreDame. 2023. Fighting For Our Cultural Heritage. University of Notre Dame. (YouTube video, 1.9.2023, duration 2:00). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VwJBAXK41Ok> (accessed 17.07.2024)
- Archaic, Pid obstrilamy: Tsyfrovyi 3D-zakhyst bronzovoho viku Ukrainy [Under fire: Digital 3D defense of Ukraine's Bronze Age]. <https://archaic.com.ua/projects/under-the-shelling-digital-3d-protection-of-the-ukrainian-bronze-age/> (accessed 23.07.2024).
- Building Bridges. 2023. Building Bridges (interview). European Cultural Foundation. 22 February <https://culturalfoundation.eu/stories/cosround7-building-bridges/> (accessed 26.7.2024).
- Buiskykh, Alla, Shydlovskiy, Pavlo and Vsevolod Ivakin. 2023. Monitorynh pamiatok arkhelo-hichnoi spadshchyny ukrainy pid chas viiskovoi ahresii rf [Monitoring of the Ukrainian archaeological heritage objects during the russia's military aggression]. Kyiv collections of history, archeology, art and life 1(4): 3-15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55389/2786-5797.2023.01.01>.
- Buiskykh, Alla, Zotsenko, Ivan and Pavlo Shydlovskiy. 2022. Poperedni rezultaty monitorynhu arkhelohichnykh pamiatok u Kyieva ta Kyivskii oblasti [Preliminary results of monitoring of archaeological sites in Kyiv and Kyiv region]. Scientific and practical seminar "Protection and preservation of the archaeological heritage of Ukraine", 23.11.22. <https://ekmair.ukma.edu.ua/handle/123456789/24993> (accessed 21.7.2024).
- Centre of Ukraine .. 2022. Centre of Ukraine Opened at VMU Education Academy (news entry). Vytautas Magnus University. 16 June <https://www.vdu.lt/en/centre-of-ukraine-opened-at-vmu-education-academy/> (accessed 26.7.2024).
- Chernyshuk, Pavlo, Legal newspaper online, Arkheolohiia Ukrainy u chas viiny: v Kyievi vidbulasia preskonferentsiia [Archaeology of Ukraine during the war: a press conference was held in Kyiv]. <https://yur-gazeta.com/golovna/arheologiya-ukrayini-u-chas-viyni-v-kyievi-vidbulasya-preskonferenciya.html> (accessed 21.7.2024).
- Culture of Solidarity .. 2022. Culture of Solidarity Fund Eunic Ukraine edition announces grantees (news entry). European Cultural Foundation. 17 November <https://culturalfoundation.eu/stories/cos-eunic-ukraine-edition-grantees/> (accessed 26.7.2024).
- Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid04UZSimrvRpVKEQAS6g51bTRqstGqK99f6AzH9BrGqNMBaar97dMs9N5FZQhGxdiCl&id=1497632036&rdid=vdmSvnUzvMPn7kML (accessed 21.7.2024).
- Durbach, Andrea and Lucas Lixinski, eds. 2017. Heritage, Culture and Rights: Challenging Legal Discourses. Oxford: Hart Publishing.
- Economou, Maria. 2015. Heritage in the Digital Age. In A Companion to Heritage Studies, 1st Edition, ed. William Logan, Máiréad Nic Craith, and Ullrich Kockel, 215-228. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. DOI: [10.1002/9781118486634.ch15](https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118486634.ch15)
- Endangered heritage in Ukraine: UNESCO reinforces protective measures (press release). 2022. UNESCO. 8 March. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/endangered-heritage-ukraine-unesco-reinforces-protective-measures?hub=701> (accessed 17.7.2024).
- German Archaeological Institute, Ukrainian Archaeological Heritage. <https://www.dainst.blog/ukrainian-archaeological-heritage/> (accessed 21.7.2024).
- German Archaeological Institute, Ukrainian Archaeology: Rich Heritage at Great Risk, 2023, <https://www.dainst.blog/ukrainian-archaeological-heritage/2023/07/14/ukrainian-archaeology-rich-heritage-at-great-risk/> (accessed 21.7.2024).
- HERI. 2023. Heritage Emergency Response Initiative: Preserving Ukraine's Cultural Heritage. <https://heri.in.ua/en/index.html> (accessed 26.07.2024).
- ICON. 2023. The Story of the Newly Set-up Center to Rescue Ukraine's Cultural Heritage in Lviv. <https://www.icon.org.uk/resource/lviv-centre-ukrainian-heritage.html> (accessed 15.07.2024).

International HEI responses to cultural heritage emergency in wartime Ukraine. <https://a1-data4ua.spread.name/> (accessed 10.07.2024)

Karazin University Scientific Periodicals, Chronicle of events at the Faculty of History for 2022. <https://periodicals.karazin.ua/history/article/view/22388> (accessed 23.07.2024).

Kazantseva, Liliia, Samoilenko, Liubov and Nataliia Pysarevska. 2023. Unversytetski muzei i viina v Ukraini [University Museums and the War in Ukraine]. *Vita Antiqua* 14: 72-92. DOI: [10.37098/VA-2023-14-72-92](https://doi.org/10.37098/VA-2023-14-72-92).

Kharkiv-Day, Derzhavnyi muzei pryrody Kharkivskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni V. Karazina [State Museum of Nature of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University], 2024. <https://kharkiv-day.com/karazin-museum-of-nature/> (accessed 23.07.2024).

Kuijt, Ian, Shydlovskyy, Pavlo, and Donaruma, William. 2024. Spotighting War's Cultural Destruction in Ukraine. *Sapiens*, 9 April. <https://www.sapiens.org/archaeology/ukraine-cultural-heritage-war-destruction/> (accessed 17.07.2024)

Latysh, Kateryna and Viktoriya Didenko. 2023. The Ukraine Center: a Cultural Bridge for Ukrainians between the Regions in Lithuania (report). Kurk Lietuvai. 20 April <https://data.kurklit.lt/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Current-situation-analysis.pdf> (accessed 26.7.2024).

Lee, Eric Yong Joong and Olimpia Niglio, Olimpia. 2019. *Cultural Diplomacy & Heritage*. Roma: tab edizioni.

Lingle, Paul, Skendzel, Dan, and Votava, Lenette. 2024. In Global Classroom, Notre Dame and Ukrainian students examine impact of war through poetry and drama. Ukrainian Catholic University, Humanities faculty. <https://humaniora.ucu.edu.ua/en/news/in-global-classroom-notre-dame-and-ukrainian-students-examine-impact-of-war-through-poetry-and-drama/> (accessed 17.07.2024)

Lviv Polytechnic National University. 2023. The Center for the Salvation of Cultural Heritage has been opened in the Scientific and Technical Library of the University. <https://pnu.ua/en/news/center-salvation-cultural-heritage-has-been-opened-scientific-and-technical-library-university> (accessed 26.07.2024).

Mynizhyn, Muzeinyi kompleks NDU im. M.Hoholia: perypetii poriatunku ta diialnosti v chasy viiny [The Museum Complex of the N.N. Gogol National State University: the Vicissitudes of Rescue and Activity in Wartime], 2022. <https://mynizhyn.com/news/misto-i-region/25828-muzeinii-kompleks-ndu-im-mgogolja-peripetiyi-porjatunku-ta-dijalnosti-v-chasi-viini.html> (accessed 23.07.2024).

NASU Institute of Archaeology, Monitorynh arkheolohichnykh obektiv pid chas viiny [Monitoring of archaeological sites during the war]. <https://iananu.org.ua/novini/ekspeditsiji/1219-monitoring-arkheologichnykh-ob-ektiv-pid-chas-vijni> (accessed 21.7.2024).

Pipenger, Michael. 2023. Finding Strength in Solidarity. *Opening Minds* (blog). 20 July <https://www.iie.org/blog/finding-strength-in-solidarity/> (accessed 17.07.2024)

Rosén, Frederik. 2022. Introduction. *Cultural Heritage and Armed Conflict: Preserving Art While Protecting Life*. In *The Preservation of Art and Culture in Times of War*, eds. Claire Finkelstein, Derek Gillman, and Frederik Rosén, 1-22. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Saint Sophia's Inscriptions <https://saintsophia.dh.gu.se/> (accessed 7.01.2025.)

Scientific Society of Students of the Faculty of History of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Panelna dyskusiia arkheolohichna spadshchyna v umovakh viiskovykh konfliktiv v Ukraini [Panel discussion Archaeological heritage in the context of military conflicts in Ukraine]. <https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=928051252455570&set=pcb.928051435788885> (accessed 21.7.2024).

Shydlovskyy, Pavlo, Kuijt, Ian, Skorokhod, Viacheslav, Zotsenko, Ivan, Ivakin, Vsevolod, Donaruma, Willian and Sean Field. 2023. The tools of war: conflict and the destruction of Ukrainian cultural heritage. *Antiquity* 97(396): 1-7. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2023.159>.

Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Naukovi ta pryrodnychi muzei svitu online [Science and natural history museums of the world online]. <http://hnpu.edu.ua/uk/naukovi-ta-pryrodnychi-muzeyi-svitu-online> (accessed 23.07.2024).

Tardy, Thierry. 2022. Ukraine, NATO, and the Madrid Strategic Concept. In *War in Europe: preliminary lessons*, NDC Research Papers Series, ed. Thierry Tardy, 13-24. Rome: NATO Defense College.

Turchynovskyy, Volodymyr (ed.). 2024. Resilient Universities. Integral Human Development Series. Lviv: Ukrainian Catholic University. <https://www.iiecitexts.ucu.edu.ua/resilient-universities> (accessed 17.07.2024)

Ukrainian South, Okupatsiina vlada rozghrabuvala muzei khersonskoho derzhavnoho universytetu [The occupation authorities looted the museum of Kherson State University], 2022. <https://pivdenukraine.com.ua/2022/11/27/okupacijna-vlada-rozgrabuvala-muzej-xersonskogo-derzhavnogo-universitetu/> (accessed 23.07.2024).

UMAC, Meeting with Ukrainian university museum professionals. <http://umac.icom.museum/meeting-with-ukrainian-university-museum-professionals/> (accessed 23.07.2024).

UNESCO. 1990. Decision 14 COM VII.A. Inscription: Kiev: Saint Sophia Cathedral and related monastic buildings, Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra. C 527ter. UNESCO, World Heritage List. Nr. CC-90/CONF.004/2. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/decisions/3572> (accessed 15.07.2024)

UNESCO. 2023. Decision 45 COM 7B.59. Kyiv: Saint-Sophia Cathedral and Related Monastic Buildings, Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra (Ukraine) (C 527ter). UNESCO. Nr. WHC/23/45.COM/7B.Add. <https://whc.unesco.org/archive/2023/whc23-45com-7B.Add-en.pdf> (accessed 15.07.2024)

UNESCO. 2023. Ukraine: 20 cultural properties receive enhanced protection by UNESCO's Second Protocol to the 1954 Hague Convention. <https://ukraine.un.org/en/245113-ukraine-20-cultural-properties-receive-enhanced-protection-unesco%E2%80%99s-second-protocol-1954> (accessed 25.07.2024).

UNITAR. 2023. UNESCO and UN Satellite Centre join forces to safeguard Ukraine's cultural heritage with geospatial technologies. <https://www.unitar.org/about/news-stories/news/unesco-and-un-satellite-centre-join-forces-safeguard-ukraines-cultural-heritage-geospatial> (accessed 26.07.2024).

University actors as agents of change in digital cultural heritage for crisis responsiveness. <https://a2-data4ua.spread.name/> (accessed 10.07.2024)

University of Gothenburg. 2024a. Researchers document thousand-year-old graffiti in Kyiv. University of Gothenburg. <https://www.gu.se/en/news/researchers-document-thousand-year-old-graffiti-in-kyiv> (accessed 15.07.2024)

University of Gothenburg. 2024b. Digital documentation of inscriptions in the Saint Sophia Cathedral in Kyiv. Research project. University of Gothenburg. <https://www.gu.se/en/research/digital-documentation-of-inscriptions-in-the-saint-sophia-cathedral-in-kyiv#theory-and-method> (accessed 15.07.2024)

University of Notre Dame. 2023. Fighting for our cultural heritage. University of Notre Dame. <https://fightingfor.nd.edu/2023/fighting-for-our-cultural-heritage/> (accessed 17.07.2024)

Verbytska, Polina and Svitlana Muravska. 2023. Museum Activists as Agents of Social Change in War. *Museum & Society* 21 (2): 51-57. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.29311/mas.v21i2.4296>

Yizhakultura. 2023. The right to practice science. The Second Scientific and Practical Conference "Food in History" – Part I. https://eng.yizhakultura.com/material/20230125_1748 (accessed 25.07.2024).

Zagoriy Foundation. 2023. To share and cook for everyone: War Cookbook explores how Ukrainians eat during the war. <https://media.zagoriy.foundation/velyka-istoriya/dilytysya-ta-gotuvaty-na-vsih-war-cookbook-doslidzhuye-yak-ukrayinczi-yidyat-pid-chas-vijny/> (accessed 26.07.2024).

Dediščina v sili: Ukrajina

Ruska invazija l.2022 je povzročala izredne razmere za celo Ukrajino, državo in ljudi kot tudi za kulturno dediščino. Največ odzivov so se osredotočali na neposredne naloge, kot so zaščita življenj civilistov ter boj za ohranitev nacionalne suverenosti in ozemeljske celovitosti, vendar se v času vojne krepita tudi pomen preteklosti in torej vloga dediščine. Zato smo pregledali pobude visokošolskih ustanov ni podrobneje analizirali sedem študij primerov za vpogled v naslednja vprašanja: Kako se je družba med vojno mobilizirala okoli kulturne dediščine? Kako so se visokošolske ustanove odzvale področju kulturne dediščine v Ukrajini? Kakšne pobude so bile izvedene, katera mednarodna sodelovanja so bila razvita in kdo so glavni akterji na institucionalni ravni? Katere prioritete so so bile za zaščito kulturne dediščine med vojno in kako pomembne so digitalne zmogljivosti?

Študije primerov pobud znotraj in onkraj Ukrajine so bile naslednje:

(1) Center za reševanje kulturne dediščine (CRCH) se je ustanovil 1. 3. 2022 za prepoznavanje ogroženih predmetov, zagotavljanje potrebnih sredstev za ohranjanje in komunikacija z mednarodnimi partnerji glede finančne in materialne pomoči. Center zagotavlja obsežno dokumentacijo in spremljanje na objektih kulturne dediščine in služi kot logistično vozlišče za zaščito fizičnih artefaktov ter združuje takojšnje zaščitne ukrepe z dolgoročnimi strategijami za obnovo in izobraževanje.

(2) Konferenca „Hrana v zgodovini“ je evidentirala spreminjajoče trende na področju hrane povezano z vojno, od memih slik do osebnih pričevanj o vlogi hrane v vsakdanjem življenju med okupacijo kot sredstvo za lajšanje stresa, kot tudi objave „Vojne kuharske knjige“.

(3) Odbor Mednarodnega sveta muzejev (ICOM UMAC) podpira ukrajinske muzeje s potrebnimi sredstvi. Na posebnem dogodku se izmenjalo strokovnih izkušenj in so podrobne predstavitve podali predstavniki šestih muzejev. Po srečanju so muzeji prejeli veliko humanitarne pomoči različnih organizacij iz Ukrajine, Poljske, Nemčije, Švice in drugih držav.

(4) Raziskovalni projekt „Digitalna dokumentacija napisov v Sofijski katedrali v Kijevu“ izvajata Göteborška raziskovalna infrastruktura za digitalno humanistiko (GRIDH) na Univerzi v Göteborgu in Muzej Sofijske katedrale v Kijevu. V okviru projekta so z digitalnimi metodami dokumentirani napisi, najdeni v katedrali svete Sofije, kar znanstvenikom omogoča dostop do ogroženega izvornega gradiva kulturne dediščine.

(5) Raziskava „Profili odpornosti in odpornosti: Dokumentiranje ropanja, poškodb in uničenja ukrajinske kulturne dediščine“. Na podlagi dolgoletnega sodelovanja med Ukrajinsko katoliško univerzo (UCU, Ukrajina) in Univerzo Notre Dame (ND, ZDA) je ameriška univerza za en semester gostila študente v kampusu ter jim zagotovila nastanitev, življenjske stroške in druge potrebne stroške.

(6) Skupina za spremljanje arheoloških pokrajin beleži izgube na arheoloških najdiščih, do katerih pogosto privedejo vojni spopadi in uničenje pokrajine. Pri tem uporablja novo razvite metode daljinskega spremljanja arheološke dediščine in vizualne preglede arheologov na določenih lokacijah poškodb na območjih zgodovinske in kulturne plasti.

(7) Projekt „Gradimo mostove: kulturna izmenjava za vse“ je novembra in decembra 2022 izvajal Center Ukrajine na Univerzi Vytautas Magnus v Litvi, da se širšemu občinstvu v državi gostiteljici vojnih beguncev predstavljajo ukrajinska kulturna dediščina, zgodovina in različne oblike umetnosti.

Glavni zaključki iz študij primerov so:

- Artefakti so se vzdrževali in ohranjevali z različnimi metodami, npr. dokumentiranje, digitalizacija in vključevanje javnosti.
- Visokošolske ustanove so bile ključne pri izvedbi zaradi intelektualne in logistične podpore.
- Zaradi mednarodnega sodelovanja so te pobude še učinkovitejše, ker omogoča hitrejše raziskave in opredeljuje dodatni potrebi po sredstvih in strokovnem znanju.

Acknowledgements

The publication was written within the project “Capacity building for data-driven cultural heritage management in Ukraine” (No. 2023-1-LV01-KA220-HED-000166558, funded by the European Union within the Erasmus+ Programme).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the State Education Development Agency of the Republic of Latvia. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**